

Effectiveness of small- and large-scale Nature-Based Solutions for flood mitigation: The case of Ayutthaya, Thailand

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Traditional grey flood mitigation measures are no longer achieving desirable results.
- NBS have a potential to be more effective and sustainable than traditional measures.
- Large/small scale NBS and their hybrid combination with grey measures were analysed.
- Numerical models and stakeholders inputs were used to analyse measures' effectiveness.
- Effective mitigation of floods from large rainfall events requires hybrid measures.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

There is growing evidence that traditional response to floods and flood-related disaster is no longer achieving desirable results. Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) represent a relatively new response towards disaster risk reduction, water security, and resilience to climate change, which has a potential to be more effective and sustainable than traditional measures. However, in practice, these measures are still being applied at a slow rate while traditional grey infrastructure remains as a preferred choice. This can be attributed to several barriers which range from political and governance to social and technological/technical. More generally, there is a lack of sufficient knowledge base to accelerate their wider acceptance and uptake. The present work provides contribution in this direction and addresses the question of effectiveness of different types of NBS (i.e., small- and large-scale NBS) and their hybrid combinations with grey infrastructure. The work has been applied on the case of Ayutthaya, Thailand. The results suggest that the effectiveness of small-scale NBS is limited to smaller rainfall events whereas the larger (or extreme) events necessitate combinations of different kinds of measures with different scales of implementation (i.e., hybrid measures).

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1. Introduction

It has become a well-accepted fact that the continuous pursuit for economic growth, exploitation of natural resources and inappropriate

developments are now paying off with severe restrictions in our possibilities to achieve environmentally sustainable and socially just world. Historically, many of our interventions have been disconnected from the nature and the problems encountered were isolated and only affected certain communities in certain ways. However, nowadays, these problems are counterless and the resulting situation has evolved into a global crisis. This is evident through unprecedented records of environmental degradation, loss of biodiversity and climate change, to name a few.

There is growing evidence that floods and flood-related disasters are the most frequent cause of devastation for economies and people around the world when compared to any other types of disasters (EEA, 2012, 2016; IPCC, 2012). Traditional responses and interventions have focused on grey infrastructure approaches (a.k.a., hard, conventional or engineering solutions) such as pipes, canals, tunnels, dikes, and the like. These measures are implemented with hard-engineered materials and as such they have created false sense of security. As a result of that, many governments and communities trust such structures to protect them from floods and in case of failure they often find themselves underprepared to cope with the effects. Several authors have documented that such infrastructure has not been effective in achieving adequate flood protection, cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability (see for example, Brink et al., 2016).

A new response towards disaster risk reduction, water security, and resilience to climate change, which has a potential to be more effective and sustainable than traditional measures, has been advocated by researchers and practitioners (Kabisch et al., 2017). That response is currently passing under the name of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS), although the literature to date shows a variety of terms which have been interchangeably used in the context of hydro-meteorological risk reduction (Ruangan et al., 2020). NBS is a term that refers to innovative solutions for solving a range of societal and environmental challenges based on natural processes and ecosystems. NBS use nature and natural processes to reduce disaster risk and enhance environmental and social benefits (Nesshöver et al., 2017; Raymond et al., 2017; Dorst et al., 2019). As such, they offer the necessary means to break away from traditional practices and better align our developments with the nature so that we can achieve more environmentally sound, socially acceptable and economically viable results.

In view of the above, there is an increasing trend in recognising the importance of NBS globally. They have been discussed, either directly or indirectly, in various European Commission policy instruments (e.g., Water Framework Directive, Floods Directive, Action Plan on the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030, EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, etc.) in addressing climate change mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity crisis, and providing a cross-cutting approach to the Sustainable Development Goals. Their importance has also been acknowledged by numerous international bodies and panels such as the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, the Convention on Biological Diversity, the Intergovernmental Panel on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services, and the United Nations Environmental Programme. Recently, in September 2019, a NBS coalition was launched at the UN Climate Summit in New York City.

In academia, a significant rise of NBS-related articles has been observed (see Ruangan et al., 2020) and several authors have addressed the effectiveness of NBS for flood risk reduction (Kong et al., 2017; Zölch et al., 2017; Versini et al., 2018). However, in practice, these measures are still being applied at a slow rate while grey infrastructure remains as a preferred choice (Dhakal and Chevalier, 2017; Qiao et al., 2018). This situation can be attributed to several barriers which range from political (e.g., NBS require longer periods of time to generate benefits while politicians tend to prioritise investments to those interventions that generate outcomes in shorter or immediate future), governance (e.g., many water and environmental management authorities operate in silos and often follow different visions, goals and regulatory frameworks while successful implementation of NBS requires full cross-sectoral cooperation), social (e.g., NBS represent a relatively new

approach and there can be a negative perception due to uncertain outcomes and preference towards traditional hard engineering “grey infrastructure”) and technological. From the technological (or technical) point of view, limited implementation of NBS for flood risk reduction is mainly due to the lack of sufficient technical references, design standards and guidelines (Qiao et al., 2018). Furthermore, there is still a general perception that the construction and especially maintenance of NBS are more costly than traditional grey infrastructure measures (see for example, Dhakal and Chevalier, 2017). Therefore, a more substantial knowledge and evidence-base is needed in order to promote their wider acceptance and upscaling/uptake (Kabisch et al., 2017).

The literature to date shows that ‘hybrid’ solutions, which effectively provide the combination of the two worlds (engineering “grey infrastructure” and ecosystem-based approaches), offer a more viable way forward. In this approach, traditional grey solutions are complemented by NBS while taking advantages of both (see for example, Dong et al., 2017; Kabisch et al., 2017; Xie et al., 2017; Haghghatafshar et al., 2018; Browder et al., 2019). If implemented properly, such combinations of solutions have the potential to create a new generation of responses, which can enhance the performance of drainage systems, protect communities, and achieve robustness and flexibility over longer periods of time (see also, EEA, 2012; Browder et al., 2019). The present work provides contribution in this direction and it addresses the question of effectiveness of different types of NBS (i.e., small- and large-scale NBS) and their hybrid combinations with grey infrastructure. The work has been applied in the case of Ayutthaya in Thailand, a region that is often subject to floods.

2. Scale of implementation

The question of scale has always been an important question in the natural and social sciences (Lovell et al., 2003; Steinhardt and Volk, 2003; Hiller et al., 2016). Understanding temporal and spatial characteristics of new practices, concepts and solutions is crucial for determining future research directions, replicability, upscaling potential and cost effectiveness. In terms of the scale of implementation of NBS, these solutions can be divided into small- and large-scale solutions. Small-scale NBS are solutions implemented at the urban or local scale, for instance in buildings, streets or roofs whereas large-scale NBS are solutions implemented at the regional scale in rural and mountainous areas and/or river basins and coastal zones (see also Ruangan et al., 2020).

Typical examples of small-scale NBS are green roofs, rain gardens, rainwater harvesting, dry detention ponds, permeable pavements, bio-retention, vegetated swales and trees. A range of examples of large-scale NBS can be found in the Dutch “Room for the River Programme”. This programme combines implementation of solutions such as floodplain lowering, dike relocation, groyne lowering, summer bed deepening, water storage, bypass channels and floodways, obstacle removal, and dike strengthening (Klijn et al., 2013). Other examples of large-scale NBS are large retention basins, lakes, wetlands, forests, terraces, etc. Typical examples of coastal NBS are mangroves, mudflats, dunes, beach nourishment and coral reefs.

To date, the effectiveness of small-scale NBS has been in the focus of researchers and only few studies have looked into the performance and effectiveness of large-scale NBS (Ruangan et al., 2020). Furthermore, very few studies explored the effectiveness of their hybrid combinations (Alves et al., 2016, 2020; Vojinovic et al., 2016b; Onuma and Tsuge, 2018).

Implementation of small-scale NBS for flood risk mitigation aims to achieve the following objectives: flood peak reduction (Ercolani et al., 2018; Mei et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018), flood peak delay (Ishimatsu et al., 2017) and reduction of runoff volume (Lee et al., 2013; Shafiqe and Kim, 2018). Green roofs perform better in reducing peak flows for small and frequent storms (see for example, Ercolani et al., 2018), while rain gardens cope more effectively with small quantities of rainwater (Ishimatsu et al., 2017). The work of Zölch et al. (2017) indicates that the effectiveness of such measures is directly related to their storage

capacity and availability of open spaces. Damodaram et al. (2010) found that the combination of rainwater harvesting and permeable pavements can be effective for small rainfall events, while storage ponds are expected to perform better for larger events. Furthermore, several studies suggest that the combination of multiple NBS can result in a more effective strategy than their single implementation (Webber et al., 2018).

One of the strong points about NBS is their ability to provide multiple secondary benefits, or *co-benefits* (i.e. Dagenais et al., 2017). Terms *benefits* and *co-benefits* refer to primary and secondary functions of NBS. In case of hydro-meteorological risk reduction, benefits would typically refer to the reduction of floodwater depth, flood extent and flood duration, while the co-benefits would refer to aspects such as energy saving, amenity, aesthetics and human well-being.

Regardless of the promising results from small-scale NBS there is an increasing body of evidence that such solutions are not sufficient to control runoff from extreme rainfall events indicating that implementation of large-scale NBS would be necessary for such cases (European Commission, 2012; Giacomoni et al., 2012; Qin et al., 2013; Demuzere et al., 2014; Ishimatsu et al., 2017; Ercolani et al., 2018). Large-scale NBS are suitable for extreme events due to their capacity to make more space for water, mitigating the risk through retention, deceleration, infiltration, etc. (Cheng et al., 2017; Thorslund et al., 2017). However, there is a large gap between the research efforts concerning small- and large-scale NBS, as small-scale interventions have received greater attention (see Ruangpan et al., 2020). One of the reasons that only few articles address effectiveness of large-scale NBS can be attributed to the fact that these solutions are more demanding in relation to their scale and complexity of processes. Hence, further research is necessary to explore effectiveness of small- and large-scale NBS and their hybrid combinations with grey infrastructure.

In this work, we address the question of effectiveness of small- and large-scale NBS and their hybrid combinations with grey infrastructure for flood risk reduction. The measures are evaluated under three scenarios: combination of small-scale NBS and local grey infrastructure measures (Scenario 1), combination of large-scale NBS and local grey infrastructure measures (Scenario 2) and combination of small- and large-scale NBS and local grey infrastructure measures (Scenario 3).

3. Methodological approach

3.1. Study area

The case study area used in the present work is Ayutthaya Island in Thailand, Fig. 1. This area is situated within the Chao Phraya River basin. The average precipitation ranges between 1092 and 1600 mm annually. The driest month is January, with an average of 1 day of precipitation,

and the wettest month is September, with an average of 21 days of precipitation.

Phra Nakorn Si Ayutthaya city often experiences problems due to pluvial and fluvial floods. The city is located in the Phra Nakorn Si Ayutthaya province which is about 80 km north of Bangkok. It is considered as an island in view of the three surrounding rivers, namely Chao Phraya River, Pasak River, and Lop Buri River. The island has an area of 7 km².

Terrain elevations are relatively low and range at around 4 m Above Mean Sea Level (AMSL). The main fluvial flood protection of the city (or the island) is the U-Thong road dike which has an elevation of 5.3 m AMSL. In terms of the pluvial floods, there is an existing drainage system comprised of pipes, lined canals, gates and pumping stations which unfortunately does not provide adequate flood protection, Fig. 2.

Roachanakanan (2013), pointed that climate change is a dominant factor contributing to increase in flood hazards in this area, since tropical storms are expected to increase in frequency and intensity (see also Shrestha, 2013). The drainage system within the island consists of pipes and canals and it is a combined drainage system. Khlong Thor and Khlong Ma Kham Rieng are the main canals to drain combined wastewater and stormwater to the Watergates where pumping stations are located. The stormwater runoff moves from the centre to east and west directions, drains through main canals from the north to the south, and it is pumped out to the Chao Phraya and Pa Sak Rivers. There are also two ponds in this area, one located in the middle of the island (Bung Phra Ram) and the other located in the southwest part. The pond in Bung Phra Ram area is a retention pond that sits within a recreational park. There is yet a third pond which is situated on a vacant land and currently receives very little attention for maintenance.

The soils at Ayutthaya have high clay and low sand contents. The soil in the area is categorized as group 2, which is described as a clay soil with a depth of 50–100 cm, and a very low permeability in the range of 0.03–0.12 m/day (DGR, 2011). There are several aquifers in the region and the main aquifer is currently between 10 and 15 m below the surface and it is called “Bangkok aquifer”, see Buapeng et al. (2006). Buapeng et al. (2006) also confirms the problem of land subsidence due to groundwater extraction in this area.

In terms of the land use, approximately one third of the area (i.e., 289 ha) is covered by the World Heritage Site (WHS), while the rest of the area is residential and commercial. The residential and commercial areas can be classified as low, medium and high-density zones.

3.2. Engagement of stakeholders

In view of the land characteristics and presence of cultural heritage assets, there are practically no possibilities for implementation of medium- and large-scale flood protection measures within the Ayutthaya Island

Fig. 1. Location of Ayutthaya City in Thailand.

Fig. 2. Urban drainage and flood protection in Ayutthaya Island.

(see also Vojinovic et al., 2016a, 2016b). Hence, the possibilities for implementation of such measures require considerations of options outside from the Ayutthaya Island which in turn necessitates involvement of a wider group of stakeholders (local and regional).

In the present work, two methods for engagement of stakeholders (i.e., public authorities, international agencies and groups, private sector and residents) were applied: one is through a questionnaire and the other is through face-to-face interviews. Both of these methods aimed at collecting opinions about different flood protection measures.

Interviews were conducted with the most active stakeholders that come from Ayutthaya municipality, local and regional authorities as well as from a number of representatives of local communities (33 people were interviewed). Information received enhanced understanding of stakeholders' perceptions and preferences towards different measures (NBS as well as grey infrastructure measures).

In terms of the small-scale NBS, a questionnaire that includes 15 questions was distributed to stakeholders. This questionnaire also included the list of possible benefits and co-benefits that can be obtained from such measures and stakeholders were asked to select those that are most desirable to them. Finally, 42 stakeholders provided their answers and this information was used for the selection of small-scale NBS. The effectiveness of the selected measures was evaluated through numerical modelling.

3.3. Numerical modelling framework

The models used in the present work consist of 1-dimensional (1D) and 2-dimensional (2D) models within the MIKE URBAN and MIKE FLOOD systems developed by DHI. Instantiation of these models required collection and processing of various kinds of data which range from terrain topography, river and drainage system geometry to hydrological and socio-economic data. For the assessment of possible measures, the following data and information were used: land use, drainage system characteristics, availability of open areas and preferences from local and regional stakeholders. To estimate impervious areas within the case study area, the method based on Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) in ArcGIS was used.

In view of the complexity, interaction and size of the two river basins (Ta Chin and Chao Praya) and given that the focus of the present work was on the Ayutthaya Island, three models were instantiated and used in the analysis, Fig. 3. Implementation of large-scale NBS, and grey and small-scale solutions were represented in regional models 1 and 2 and local models 3, Fig. 3. Simulations from the first and second models provide boundary conditions for the third model, i.e., the 1D-2D model of Ayutthaya Island.

For modelling small-scale NBS, the LID toolbox within MIKE URBAN was used and for large-scale NBS the river network was modified to include different structures. Synthetic rainfall events of 2 yr, 20 yr and 100 yr Average Recurrence Intervals (ARI) were used for the subsequent analysis of measures. In addition, the present work also took into consideration the large event that took place in 2011 which corresponds to the 100 yr ARI event.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Selection of grey infrastructure measures

In terms of the traditional grey infrastructure measures, the following measures were considered: alteration/raising of dikes height, construction of gates, amplification of the drainage system and improvement of the pumping strategy, rehabilitation of ancient canals and construction of flood walls along the river. These were first presented to the stakeholders and then ranked on the basis of their preferences, Fig. 4. Alteration of the height of the U-Thong Road dike was found to be the most preferred measure. The second preferred measure was an amplification of the existing drainage system, canals and rivers. Other less preferred measures are construction of the gate at the Klong Mueng location, rehabilitation of ancient canals and construction of retaining walls along the rivers Fig. 4.

In terms of the rehabilitation of ancient canals, this measure was requested by one of the stakeholders. Currently, most of the ancient canals do not exist as they are filled up and turned into roads and encroached by the buildings. Field investigation revealed that some parts of ancient

Fig. 3. Modelling framework: (1) 1D model of the Ta Chin River basin and the Lower Chao Praya River basin, (2) 1D model of the Chao Praya River basin and (3) 1D–2D models of the Ayutthaya Island.

canals could be reinstated into canals. This measure could increase the total capacity of canals from 0.37 Mm³ to 0.55 Mm³, which represents an increase in the storage volume for about 48% and as such it was used in the analysis.

4.2. Selection of small- and large-scale NBS

The possibilities for implementation of small-scale NBS are based on the analysis of current land use, terrain elevations and features, drainage system characteristics, availability of open areas and preferences from local and regional stakeholders. From the analysis of such data the following surface areas were identified in GIS: flat roofs, parking lots, low traffic roads, parks and playfields, transportation corridors and other open green spaces. These surfaces provide suitable areas for a range of

small-scale NBS (e.g., green roofs, bio-retention, pervious/porous pavements, infiltration trenches, swales, etc.). Fig. 5 depicts the outcome from the spatial analysis.

The possibilities for larger implementation of small-scale NBS within the World Heritage Site (WHS) were not considered since this area is under national and UNESCO cultural heritage protection. The Fine Arts Department (Ministry of Culture) came up with the possibility that some of these measures (i.e., permeable pavements) could be implemented in areas with parking lots and these measures were subsequently used in the analysis.

Furthermore, the idea of constructing a network of ponds and/or enlarging some of the existing ponds in the south-west area of the island was separately presented and discussed with stakeholders, Fig. 6. From field investigations and model simulations it was found that the existing

Fig. 4. Illustration of the preferences received from Ayutthaya residents regarding grey infrastructure measures.

Fig. 5. Spatial analysis of possibilities for implementation of small-scale NBS.

pond capacity of 0.52 Mm^3 could be enlarged to accommodate 1.5 Mm^3 to increase the total pond capacity for about 300%. The goal would be to create the flood detention area as a multifunctional space with different purposes such as flood control, recreation, art and cultural activities, rice

farms and floating markets, Fig. 7. This idea received positive response from all stakeholders and it was used in the subsequent analysis.

The questionnaire that was given to stakeholders aimed to ascertain preferences towards desired benefits and co-benefits from possible NBS

Fig. 6. Illustration of a possible network of ponds within the WHS.

Fig. 7. Illustration of a multifunctional design of detention ponds in Ayutthaya.

sites. The benefits from NBS are related to flood reduction aspects such as reduction of floodwater depths, extents and durations, while the co-benefits are divided into three categories: environmental, social, and economic, Table 1. For further details concerning engagement of stakeholders see Alves et al. (2018).

The analysis of desired benefits and co-benefits gave further direction into the selection of measures. The co-benefits such as amenity, aesthetics, recreation and health improvements could be achieved through a network of ponds, vegetative swales, bio-retentions and green roofs. These measures could be also effective for enhancing biodiversity and ecology. Rainwater harvesting can be achieved through rain barrels, pervious pavements and infiltration trenches. Water quality improvements can be achieved through implementation of bio-retentions, pervious pavements, infiltration trenches and vegetative swales. Furthermore, energy savings can be achieved by implementing green roofs, pervious pavements and ponds.

Finally, from the overall analysis, seven types of small-scale NBS were identified as feasible and used in the subsequent work Table 2.

With respect to the large-scale NBS in the Ayutthaya region, the measures evaluated in the present work are the measures proposed in JICA (2013) and JICA (2018) reports. These are: Ayutthaya Bypass Channel and widening of the Bang Ban and Thung Ma Kham Yong Ponds, Table 3 and Fig. 8. The main objective of these large-scale measures is to provide an additional storage and conveyance capacity next to the Chao Phraya River and subsequently reduce high river flows entering the Ayutthaya Island.

The three main large-scale NBS (ABC, BBP and TMKYP, Table 3) were presented to stakeholders and analysed in relation to their preferences. Fig. 9 illustrates the findings from stakeholders' preferences.

Table 1
An overview of benefits and co-benefits defined by local and regional stakeholders.

Environmental benefits		Social benefits		Economic benefits	
Biodiversity and ecology	Water quality	Amenity and aesthetics	Recreation and health	Rainwater harvesting	Energy savings
38%	29%	50%	43%	48%	24%

Besides the flood-related benefits such as rainfall interception, storage and conveyance, these measures also offer sustainable solutions for nutrient retention and carbon sequestration. They are also likely to bring a range of regional values by enhancing biodiversity, habitat characteristics, water chemistry variables, amenity, aesthetics, recreation and human well-being.

4.3. Development of scenarios for assessment of measures

Within the scope of the present work the following three scenarios were addressed:

- Scenario 1 (S1): combinations of small-scale NBS with grey infrastructure measures,
- Scenario 2 (S2): combinations of large-scale NBS with grey infrastructure measures, and
- Scenario 3 (S3): combinations of small- and large-scale NBS with local grey infrastructure measures.

Table 2
Selected small-scale NBS.

Small-scale NBS	Abbr.
Bio-retention	BR
Pervious pavement	PP
Rain barrel	RB
Green roof	GR
Infiltration trench	IT
Vegetative swale	VS
Network of Ponds within WHS	NPWHS

Table 3
Selected large-scale NBS.

Large-scale NBS	Abbr.
Ayutthaya Bypass Channel	ABC
Bang Ban Pond	BBP
Thung Ma Kham Yong Pond	TMKYP

Fig. 8. Illustration of large-scale NBS: Ayutthaya Bypass Channel and widening of the Bang Ban and Thung Ma Kham Yong Ponds.

As mentioned previously, the synthetic rainfall data of 2 yr, 20 yr and 100 yr ARI events was used in the analysis. In addition, the data from the event that took place in 2011, which caused large-scale floods across the country, and which was regarded as an extreme event, was also used in the analysis.

4.3.1. Analysis of effects from small-scale NBS and grey infrastructure (Scenario 1)

Initially, the effectiveness of small-scale NBS was assessed in relation to runoff volume reduction and runoff peak flow reduction. This was done within the MIKE URBAN hydrodynamic model using the hydrological kinematic wave model of the LID toolbox.

The total area was divided into three catchments, see Fig. 10. Catchments 1 and 3 are predominantly urbanized while catchment area 2 is not very urbanized as it sits within the World Heritage Site area. The average terrain slope in all three catchments is approximately 1%.

Catchment area 3 is the largest area and it contains the highest percentage of imperviousness (i.e., 52%), Catchment area 1 is 41% impervious whereas Catchment area 2 has the lowest percentage of imperviousness (i.e., 24%). The findings from the spatial analysis in all three catchments were used as inputs into the numerical model, Table 4.

The runoff discharges from these three catchments were obtained by running the hydrological MIKE URBAN model for different return periods. The time series of runoff discharges for 2 years return period for three catchments are given in Fig. 11. This result represents the baseline situation (i.e., existing situation without implementation of NBS) against which the performance of different NBS (i.e., runoff volume reduction and runoff peak reduction) was assessed.

For setting up small-scale NBS into the MIKE URBAN model different variables were applied. The values for these variables are obtained from the literature review and presented in Appendix A.

The results from MIKE URBAN model are summarised in Fig. 12. The results show that the application of small-scale NBS can be effective for low return period events. Their effectiveness is reduced by 67% in terms of the runoff volume reduction and by 81% in terms of the peak runoff reduction when compared to the results between 2-year and 100-year return periods. This finding is in line with the literature to date suggesting that such measures are more effective for low return period events and not very effective for larger events.

Furthermore, we have also carried out simulations with the event that occurred in 2011 and the result from that simulation is given in Fig. 13. Fig. 13 shows that these measures are not effective for an event of such magnitude. Hence, to cope with larger (or extreme) events, it would be necessary to combine these measures with large-scale NBS.

Fig. 9. Illustration of the preferences received from Ayutthaya residents regarding large-scale NBS.

Fig. 10. Catchments division.

Table 4
Inventory of potential sites for placement of small-scale NBS in the study area.

Type of area	C1		C2		C3		Total	
	Area		Area		Area		Area	
	m ²	%	m ²	%	m ²	%	m ²	%
Buildings (Number)	1374	0.1%	1070	0.04%	6285	0.2%	8729	0.1%
Flat roofs	802	0.1%	0	0.0%	35,019	1.0%	35,821	0.5%
Parking lots/Low traffic areas	12,587	1.4%	42,430	1.6%	58,818	1.8%	113,835	1.6%
Parks and playfields	25,986	2.8%	0	0.0%	76,611	2.3%	102,597	1.5%
Transportation corridors	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	42,381	1.3%	42,381	0.6%
Green spaces	15,785	1.7%	4027	0.1%	66,124	2.0%	85,936	1.2%
Total	56,534	6.1%	47,527	1.7%	285,237	8.5%	389,298	5.6%

Fig. 11. Time series of runoff discharges per catchment (2 years ARI).

Fig. 12. Effectiveness of different small-scale NBS for different return periods (BR: bio-retention, PP: pervious pavement, RB: rain barrel, GR: green roof, VS: vegetative swale, and IT: infiltration trench). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 13. Effectiveness of small-scale NBS for 2011 flood event (i.e., an event similar to 100 yr ARI event); 1D–2D model result depicting floodwater depths.

4.3.2. Analysis of effects from large-scale NBS and grey infrastructure (Scenario 2)

The river network was instantiated in MIKE 11™ whereas the terrain topography LiDAR DEM data with 20 m resolution was used as the bathymetry input in MIKE 21™. Following Keerakamolchai (2014), the Manning’s M friction coefficient of 30 was applied to all cells in the 2D model. The drying depth was set to 0.01 m and the flood depth was set to 0.02 m. The coupling between the two models was based on lateral central links. The final 1D–2D model is illustrated in Fig. 14.

The time-series comprised of discharges and water levels were used as upstream and downstream boundary conditions for the 1D model, Fig. 14. The measurements at these points were obtained from the Royal Irrigation Department, Ministry of Agriculture and Cooperatives (RID/MOAC) and recorded during the 2011 flood event and used in

the calibration work. The initial calibration of the 1D model was undertaken in the study of Keerakamolchai (2014) and further enhanced in the present work, Figs. 15 and 16 (see also Meesuk et al., 2017). The time step used in the model simulations was set to 5 s with a simulation period from 1 July to 30 November 2011.

The analysis of effectiveness of large-scale NBS was assessed only for the 2011 event (i.e., extreme event that caused the so-called “great Thailand floods”). The return period of that event is regarded to be similar to 100 year ARI event.

The model results show that only by incorporating large-scale NBS the flood volume from such large event could be more substantially reduced. It was found that this reduction would be in the order of 22%. However, despite the substantial reduction in river flows the local pluvial floods would still remain an issue, Fig. 17. This indicates the possibility for analysing trade-offs between improvements of the local drainage system, or grey infrastructure measures, and small-scale NBS.

4.3.3. Analysis of effects from hybrid solutions (Scenario 3)

A combination of different models was used for evaluation of impacts from combined small- and large-scale NBS with grey measures. The regional model was used to evaluate the effects of large-scale NBS and for boundary conditions for the local model. The local model was used to evaluate the effects of grey measures and small-scale NBS. With this setup, the impact of regional and local measures (i.e., hybrid solution) was assessed for the rainfall event that occurred in 2011. The model results with hybrid solutions show that this would be the most effective strategy for mitigating floods in the Ayutthaya city, Figs. 18 and 19. Only by combining small- and large-scale NBS with grey infrastructure the flood volume can be reduced to a level that is desirable by stakeholders. Implementation of large-scale NBS can reduce high flow rates coming from the Chao Praya River and entering the Ayutthaya Island whereas the remaining local/pluvial floods can be mitigated effectively by small-scale NBS and grey measures (i.e., improvements in the local drainage system). Furthermore, improvements in the local drainage system would be beneficial in confining the excess floodwaters within the drainage canals and conveying them to the multifunctional ponds.

The work presented here combines measures with different scales and types which essentially reflect different worlds of application. On the one side it has to do with creating the world of traditional hard infrastructure, while on the other side it has to do with creating the world with natural surroundings as these come together to satisfy the desired levels of flood protection. Being creative processes, both are technologies where the first is constantly advancing of course, but it is the second that is advancing so much more rapidly today in view of the higher climate change mitigation and adaptation agenda. In terms of the benefits and co-benefits, the grey infrastructure is known to provide few benefits with little or no co-benefits while NBS have the potential to provide a wide range of benefits and co-benefits. However, what happens in the outer world with traditional hard infrastructure is obvious because it can be immediately visible and to a large degree tangible, while what happens with the natural

Fig. 14. Illustration of the final 1D–2D models. The time-series of discharges and water levels are set upstream (a, b and c) and downstream (d) as boundary conditions for the 1D model; 2D model simulates overland flows.

Fig. 15. Comparison of observed and computed (i.e., model simulated) water levels at C35 station (left) and S5 station (right).

Fig. 16. Comparison of observed and computed (i.e., model simulated) discharges at C35 station (left) and S5 station (right).

Fig. 17. Effectiveness of large-scale NBS for 2011 flood event (i.e., an event similar to 100 yr ARI event); 1D-2D model result depicting floodwater depths;

Fig. 18. Effectiveness of hybrid measures for 2011 flood event (i.e., an event similar to 100 yr ARI event).

Fig. 19. Illustration of hybrid measures in Ayutthaya.

systems is not necessarily immediately visible, and for some co-benefits, it usually requires longer periods of time to manifest. Thus, this is an important point for stakeholders who need to decide on the selection of measures which may initially appear as abstract and theoretical.

5. Conclusions

The present work addresses the question of effectiveness of different types of NBS (i.e., small- and large-scale NBS) and their hybrid combinations with grey infrastructure through three scenarios: combination of small-scale NBS and local grey infrastructure measures (Scenario 1), combination of large-scale NBS and local grey infrastructure measures (Scenario 2) and combination of small- and large-scale NBS and local grey infrastructure measures (Scenario 3). The analyses were carried out for the case of Ayutthaya in Thailand, which is often subject to frequent floods. The measures were first selected in consultation with local and regional stakeholders, who expressed their opinions and preferences. Thereafter, each scenario was evaluated using hydrodynamic modelling.

The results obtained are in line with the work to date and confirm that the effectiveness of small-scale NBS (i.e., Scenario 1) is rather limited with respect to the magnitude of rainfall events. For Ayutthaya, it was found that the effectiveness of such measures is reduced by 67% in terms of the runoff volume reduction and by 81% in terms of the peak runoff reduction when comparing the results between 2-year and 100-year return periods. Hence, to cope with larger (or extreme) events, it would be necessary to combine these measures with large-scale NBS and/or grey infrastructure measures. Furthermore, the results from model simulations concerning large-scale NBS (i.e., Scenario 2) show that the construction of Ayutthaya Bypass channel and widening of two ponds upstream would considerably reduce fluvial flooding in the Ayutthaya City Island. However, to mitigate local pluvial floods these measures would need to be combined with small-scale NBS and/or grey infrastructure measures.

The result shows that only Scenario 3, representing combinations between all three kinds of measures, is likely to provide a level of flood

protection that is most desirable by stakeholders. It has been argued that hybrid combinations between different solutions have a strong potential to achieve better outcomes not only in flood protection but also in biodiversity and socio-economic benefits when compared to any of the solutions when applied alone. Furthermore, implementation of such combined solutions stands better chance for acceptance by those who may be still more inclined towards engineering grey solutions, i.e., they stand better chance for overcoming barriers and gaining wider acceptance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Zoran Vojinovic: Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Visualization. **Alida Alves:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Jose Patiño Gómez:** Formal analysis, Investigation. **Sutat Weesakul:** Supervision, Investigation. **Weeraya Keerakamolchai:** Formal analysis, Methodology. **Vorawit Meesuk:** Data curation. **Arlex Sanchez:** Supervision, Project administration.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there no conflict of interest associated with this work.

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Appendix A

Table A1
NBS variables used in the MIKE URBAN model.

Category	Description	Unit	BR	PP	RB	GR	VS	IT	Sources		
			Value	Value	Value	Value	Value	Value			
0	GI properties	Initial saturation	%	0	0	0	0	0	Assumption (PSU, 2017; VWRRC, 2011; LID_Center, 2016)		
		GI area/drainage area	1/1	0.2	0.5	0.05	1	0.2			
1	Surface Storage	Storage height	mm	250	0	–	100	1000	10	(Hellberg, 2016; Assumption; DHI, 2016b)	
		Vegetation cover	–	0.6	0	–	0.6	0.1	0.1		
		Surface roughness	M	2.5	91	–	30	2	2.5		
		Swale side slope	1/1	–	–	–	–	2	–		(PSBMP, 2006)
		Surface slope	%	1	1	–	1	1	1		(DHI, 2016b)
2	Soil Geometry	Thickness	mm	1000	–	–	300	–	–	(Hellberg, 2016; DHI, 2016b)	
		Porosity	1/1	0.5	–	–	0.5	–	–		
		Field capacity	1/1	0.2	–	–	0.2	–	–		
		Wilting point	1/1	0.1	–	–	0.1	–	–		
		Infiltration capacity	mm/h	80	–	–	80	–	–		(Hellberg, 2016)
Soil Flow	Leakage capacity	mm/h	10	–	–	10	–	–	(Hellberg, 2016)		
	Thickness	mm	–	150	–	–	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)		
3	Pavement	Porosity	1/1	–	0.15	–	–	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
		Impervious surface	1/1	–	0	–	–	–	–	Assumption	
		Permeability	mm/h	–	2450	–	–	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
		Clogging factor	1/1	–	0	–	–	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
		Height	mm	450	300	900	–	–	1000	(Hellberg, 2016; DHI, 2016b; LID_Center, 2016)	
4	Storage	Porosity	1/1	0.3	0.3	–	–	–	0.3	(Hellberg, 2016; DHI, 2016b)	
		Infiltration capacity	mm	1	1	–	–	–	1	(DRG, 2011)	
		Clogging factor	%	0	0	–	–	–	0	(Hellberg, 2016; DHI, 2016b)	
		Drain capacity	mm/h	3	3	0	–	–	3	(Hellberg, 2016; DHI, 2016b)	
		Exponent	%	0.5	0.5	0.5	–	–	0.5	Assumption	
5	Underdrain	Offset	mm	100	100	0	–	–	100	(Hellberg, 2016; DHI, 2016b)	
		Delay	h	–	–	24	–	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
		Thickness	mm	–	–	–	50	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
6	Drain Mat	Void factor	1/1	–	–	–	0.95	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
		Roughness	M	–	–	–	10	–	–	(DHI, 2016b)	
		Installation cost	US \$/m ²	50	45	450	180	20	25	(LID_Center, 2016; PSU, 2017)	

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